

Protoplast fusion between V20 A and IR36 and regeneration of putative cybrid. (a) gamma-irradiated protoplasts of V20 A; (b) iodoacetamide-treated protoplasts of IR36; (c) microcolonies resulting from sustained division of the fusion product; (d) plantlets regenerated from putative cybrid calli; and (e) putative cybrid plants.

Characters of plants regenerated from protoplasts of photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile rice

Qingzhong Xue and K. Etoh, Agronomy Department, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou 310029, People's Republic of China; and S. McCouch and E. D. Earle, Plant Breeding and Biometry Department, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY 14853-1902, USA

Identifying photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterility (PGMS) in rice (Shi 1981) makes it possible to produce hybrid rice seed through the two-line system. We studied the response of PGMS protoplast clones to photoperiod and temperature,

variation in ploidy, and agronomic traits. Promising PGMS line Zhenongdal 1s (X126-11) has already been developed through protoplast culture.

A cell suspension with small globular calli was established from the scutellum of mature embryos of PGMS cultivar N5047s. A high density ($1.5 \times 10^6 \text{ ml}^{-1}$) of protoplasts was obtained, and green regenerates (plantlets) were produced following Xue and Earle's (1995) method. To distinguish autotetraploids from diploids, the DNA content of regenerates was measured using flow cytometry according to the procedure of Arumugamuthan and Earle (1991). Sowing at different times under natural conditions at Hangzhou ($30^\circ 15' \text{ N}$) promoted changes in fertility and agronomic traits of the four diploid PGMS protoplast clones and their control cultivar N5047s.

Variation in ploidy. Flow cytometric analysis indicated that nuclear DNA content in protoplasts of diploid plants ranged between 0.715 and 0.873 $\text{pg } 2c^{-1}$, and that from autotetraploids ranged between 1.537 and 1.786 $\text{pg } 2c^{-1}$. This accounted for 60% diploid plants and 40% autotetraploid plants. Diploid regenerates were taller (78.0 cm) compared with the autotetra-

ploids (44.5 cm). The diploid plants had 96.5 spikelets per panicle whereas autotetraploids had few spikelets (19.3).

Change in fertility. Typical sterile pollen was >85% at the sterile stage and ranged from 10 to 30% at the fertile stage. However, the spherical sterile pollen ranged from 5 to 20% at the two stages. Percentage of staining pollen exhibited one or three peaks at the fertile stage. Four PGMS protoplast clones had obvious differences both in duration of sterility and in stability before mid-August. The change from sterility to fertility was clear. Seed set was more than 30% under shorter daylength in September.

Agronomic traits. Agronomic characters significantly differed among the four diploid protoplast clones and control cultivar N5047s. Spikelets panicle^{-1} , panicle number plant^{-1} , spikelet density, and 100-grain weight of X126-11 were significantly higher than those of other protoplast clone and NS047s.

Photoperiod and temperature responses. We used computer simulation analysis of PGMS protoplast clones to measure photoperiod-sensitive and temperature-sensitive coefficients for defining their model of seed set rate. The

Comparison of the anatomical structure of anther connective tissue and thrum at the fertile and sterile stages X126-11. (a) Fertile anther connective tissue, (b) sterile anther connective tissue, (c) fertile thrum, and (d) sterile thrum. NVB = normal vascular bundle. AVB = abnormal vascular bundle. V = vascular bundle. S = sieve tubes.

analysis showed that photoperiod and temperature can affect fertility of PGMS protoplast clones.

Anatomical differences between and fertile periods in PGMS rice. The pollen sac and thrum (or filament) at the sterile stage were smaller than those at the fertile stage. Poorly developed vessel elements and sieve tubes of the anther vascular bundle and thrum vascular bundle (see figure) are abnormalities that can affect the transport of nutrients to the pollen sac, leading to microspore sterility.

Cited references

- Arumugamuthan K, Earle ED. 1991. Estimate of nuclear DNA content of plants by flow cytometry. *Plant Mol. Biol. Rep.* 9:229-231.
- Shi MS. 1981. Preliminary research report on breeding and utilization of natural two-uses line in late Japonica rice. *Sci. Agric. Hubei* 7:1-3.
- Xue QZ, Earle ED. 1995. Plant regeneration from protoplasts of cytoplasmic male sterile lines of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Plant Cell Rep.* 15:76-81. ■

Attempted hybridization between *Oryza sativa* L. and *Porteresia coarctata* T.

Z. I. Seraj, M. O. Faruque, Biochemistry Department, University of Dhaka (UD), Dhaka 1000, Bangladesh; K. G. Hossain, Institute of Post Graduate Studies in Agriculture, Salna, Gazipur, Bangladesh; R. H. Sarker, Botany Department, UD; T. Devi, Z. Islam, Biochemistry Department, UD; and A. S. Islam, Botany Department, UD

Wild halophytic *Porteresia coarctata* (2n=4x=48), endemic to the coastal areas in Bangladesh, is a potential source of salt tolerance for *Oryza sativa*. Crosses between these two genera were unsuccessful until Jena (1994) reported a hybrid between IR36 and *P. coarctata*. This triploid hybrid was much smaller than either parent and was completely male sterile. Sarker et al (1993) found that *P. coarctata* accepts *O. sativa* pollen readily, but not vice versa. Our crossing strategy therefore involved *P. coarctata*

(4x)/*O. sativa* (2n) and tetraploid *O. sativa* (4x-c)/*P. coarctata*.

Hand pollinations were made between the two genera. Gibberellic acid (75 ppm) with 0.1 % Tween was sprayed once 20 min after crossing. Embryos were rescued 10-12 d after pollination and cultured on 1/4 Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium with 0.45% agarose. Hybrids showing slow growth were kept on 1/4 MS for 8-10 wk. Plants were then transferred to the soil. Rapidly dividing root tips were stained with Feulgen.

Seed set percentage and survival among crosses were recorded (see table) The tetraploid hybrid from the cross BR-7 (4x-c)/*P. coarctata* grew vigorously and was taller than the induced tetraploid mother variety BR-7 (4x-c). Leaf texture was rough or intermediate between that of the parents. Leaves of the hybrid taper gradually compared with the abrupt taper of BR-7 (4x-c) leaves but not as gradually as those of *P. coarctata*. The hybrid did not set any seed on selfing. It has spikelets showing short awn and the curled morphology and asynchronized flowering pattern of *P. coarctata*. The hybrid from cross IR36/ *P. coarctata*, which showed parental isozyme bands both of *O. sativa* and *P. coarctata*, did not survive. The hybrid from BR-7(4x)/*P. coarctata* showed a faint band corresponding to that of *P. coarctata*.

Both *P. coarctata* and the tetraploid hybrid had 48 chromosomes. Chromo-

somes in the hybrid, counted from 50 cells, appear to be a mixture of the parents.

We examined 70 cells in triploid hybrids *P. coarctata* × Rajashail/Binnatoa and found them to have 36 chromosomes. The morphology of the triploid hybrid is close to that of *P. coarctata*. Three F₁s involving *P. coarctata* with Binnatoa 1, Rajashail 1, and Rajashail 4 showed 24.3, 15.3, and 30.8% seed set, respectively. Seed set in selfed *P. coarctata* was 94%. Embryos from three seeds obtained after back-crossing *P. coarctata*/Rajashail 4 with Rajashail pollen were rescued 11-13 d after anthesis and are currently being grown in 1/4 MS medium with 0.45% agarose.

Chromosomes of *P. coarctata* and *O. sativa* are small and not morphologically distinct from each other, making studies difficult on the tetraploid hybrid nature through standard karyotype analysis. We have multiplied the hybrid through vegetative propagation. We will examine it for hybridity based on meiotic chromosome and restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis.

Cited references

- Jena KK. 1994. Production of intergeneric hybrid between *Oryza sativa* L. and *Porteresia coarctata* T. *Curr. Sci.* 67:744-746.
- Sarker RH, Samad MA, Seraj ZI, Hoque MI, Islam AS. 1993. Pollen tube growth in crosses between *Porteresia coarctata* and *Oryza sativa*. *Euphytica* 67:744-746. ■

Percent seed set and survival in crosses of *O. sativa* and *P. coarctata*.

Cross combination	Seed set (%) ^a	Germinated plants (no.)	Surviving plants (no.)
IR36 (4x)/ <i>P. coarctata</i>	1.6 (180)	3	0
IR64 (4x)/ <i>P. coarctata</i>	1.6 (120)	2	0
Latisail (4x)/ <i>P. coarctata</i>	0.16 (1250)	2	0
BR-7 (4x)/ <i>P. coarctata</i>	0.44 (900)	4	1
<i>P. coarctata</i> /Rajashail (2x)	2.34 (940)	22	4
<i>P. coarctata</i> /Binnatoa (2x)	4.16 (240)	10	4
<i>P. coarctata</i> /BR-7 (2x)	2 (1140)	6	0

^aValues in parentheses indicate total number of florets used in crossing.